

The role of multiliteracies in language teaching in Greek secondary education

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This article demonstrates the results of a relevant primary research study about multiliteracies. Specifically, the purpose of the research was to investigate teachers' opinions regarding the role and position of multiliteracies in language teaching context in Greece secondary education. Semi-structured interviews were utilized for data collection, followed by thematic qualitative analysis of the transcribed research material, which was obtained from these interviews. The analysis of the results indicates that the participants have a comprehensive grasp of multiliteracies in both theory and practice. They can accurately articulate the characteristics of multiliteracies, as well as their position and role in both society and education. It appears that teachers intentionally and deliberately opt to incorporate them into language teaching, citing students' positive reaction and the consequential learning advantages. However, they express a lack of confidence and emphasize the necessity of additional training.

Keywords: Greece; Language Teaching; Multiliteracies; Secondary Education; Teachers' Views

1. Introduction

'Multiliteracies' was created as a concept to describe and highlight two key aspects of meaning making in modern societies: (a) social diversity, and (b) multimodality. The first one is linked to the linguistic, cultural and social diversity and the consequent conceptualization depending on the context while the second one links to the effect of the new media of information and communication (Cope & Kalantzis, 2009; Kalantzis & Cope, 2008; Kalantzis et al., 2019; New London Group, 1996). Therefore, multiliteracies are associated not only with the variety of text forms produced in a multilingual and multicultural society, but also with the variety of communication forms carried out through information technology and multimedia (Chatzisavvidis, 2003).

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This denotes that meaning is now created in multimodal ways “*in which written linguistic models of meaning interface with oral, visual, audio, gestural, tactile and spatial patterns of meaning*” (Kalantzis, et al., 2019, p. 14). As a consequence, these changes create new conditions in education and language teaching, highlighting the need to adapt and align learning with contemporary data. On a practical level, this means that literacy teaching should no longer focus solely on the rules and formal form of the national language alone. On the contrary, the aim of multiliteracies is to familiarize students with other resources of understanding the world apart from lingual, and prepare them appropriately so that they can be able to adapt and respond to the data and requirements of each communicative situation. This, in turn, requires thoroughly trained teachers so as to possess the ability to put all of the above into practice taking into account that in the context of multiliteracies their role is considered to be pivotal considering that they are perceived as “*designers of learning processes*” (New London Group, 1996, p. 73).

2. Background

Multiliteracies, as a concept and practice, have been at the center of scientific and educational debates in recent years, as a result of which a significant amount of research has already been published. Many of them have a purely bibliographic nature and attempt either to approach the subject conceptually or to record the relevant research. By some others, the interest is directed to official educational materials, such as curricula and school textbooks and the extent to which they align with the principles of multiliteracies. Furthermore, there is a lot of research that focuses on the design, practical implementation and utilization of multiliteracies in teaching, whilst there are notably fewer studies that examine teachers’ opinions on the particular topic. Due to the limited extent of this work, some of them will be mentioned indicatively with the main selection criterion being the common ground with the subject under consideration.

Rajendram (2015) compares twelve studies related to the use of multiliteracies in English teaching across all education levels and highlights five thematic categories related to potential student benefits: (a) student agency and ownership of learning, (b) language and literacy development, (c) affirmation of their language, culture and identity, (d) promoting collaboration among students, and (e) enhancing critical literacy skills. On the other hand, she finds that there is also an important weakness, as a clear framework for evaluating the results of such procedures and practices does not seem to exist. Therefore, she comes to the conclusion that multiliteracies pose a challenge for teachers, and their continuous support and empowerment is deemed necessary in order for them to be able to respond to the ever-increasing demands.

Boche (2014) examines how novice first-year secondary English Language teachers understand the concept of multiliteracies, and how they use them in their teaching. These educators possess the necessary theoretical knowledge, having completed relevant coursework during their undergraduate studies. For that purpose, it is examined whether it is possible for them to apply their knowledge to real classrooms and the way which something like this could be achieved. As it emerged from the research, the teachers had included multiliteracies in their teaching, mainly through the use of multimodal texts. Examining at a second level the motivations that led them to these choices, it turns out that their ultimate goal was the strengthening of the participation of students in the educational process, the consequent easier and more effective learning and the encouragement and familiarization of students with a different and ideally critical way of thinking. Simultaneously, the significance of providing support and training to teachers is underscored since it is noticed to be a necessary requirement for the effective implementation of innovative teaching methods and ensuring the overall teaching success.

Lim et al. (2020) investigate the views of primary and secondary schools' teachers who teach the language course in relation to multiliteracies. These educators connect multiliteracies to multimodal texts and technology and identify relevant references in the Curriculum. The response of students, the learning outcomes and the acquisition of valuable and necessary skills, such as the development of critical thinking and metacognitive skills are among the main reasons that lead teachers to make use of them. Nevertheless, despite the familiarity and effort to effectively integrate and utilize them in teaching, teachers express a lack of confidence in the use of multiliteracies pointing out the need for additional guidance and relevant further training.

The previous research is similar to the one conducted by Lim et al. (2022), which examines the perceptions and practices of secondary English Language teachers in relation to multiliteracies after their formal introduction into the curriculum. Data analysis reveals that teachers acknowledge the significance of multiliteracies and regard the guidance provided by the curriculum for their implementation as crucial. On a practical level, they seek to use multimodal texts and texts related to the daily experiences of their students. Nonetheless, they note that their choices can be constrained by the impact of assessments, as they tend to prioritize the content assessed in National language examinations. Moreover, many of the teachers seem not to feel particularly safe and confident about planning and implementing teaching of such kind because of the fact that they claim they have not received formal training in it. This underscores the requirement for proper teacher preparation, as well as the necessity of continual support and the updating of their knowledge.

The restrictive effect of assessment is also highlighted by the research of Kiss and Mizusawa (2018), which investigates the institutional teaching framework along with the perceptions and teaching practices of secondary school teachers who teach English as a foreign language, a second language, or as a first language. According to the results of the research, it appears that the dominant examination culture largely determines the way of teaching (see, for example, Biggs, 1988; Cheah, 1998; Peterson et al., 2007; Turvey, 2007). Consequently, there appears to be more emphasis on functional literacy through standardized procedures that will ensure success in exams rather than a pedagogy that promotes critical thinking, social equality and cultural and linguistic diversity. Teachers express their willingness to integrate components supporting a pedagogy of multiliteracies into their teaching. They highlight the significant pressure they experience and the necessity to adhere to the requirements outlined in the curriculum, though. Therefore, they employ multimodal texts acknowledging their role in enhancing student engagement and the resulting cognitive advantages. Nevertheless, they are constrained by the specific text types and approaches required in exams leaving little time for students to experiment and create their own texts.

The restrictive function of the provided educational material is also confirmed by previous research, which analyzed textbooks (Aski, 2008; Wong & VanPatten, 2003) and gathered teachers' perspectives (Allen, 2008; Askildson, 2008). According to all of them, textbooks predominantly contain form-focused mechanical exercises that prioritize a morphological approach to language. At the same time, teachers seem to have limited knowledge of alternative approaches, such as that of multiliteracies, and are reluctant to deviate from the textbook-prescribed teaching methods. Therefore, they draw the conclusion that this material constitutes a factor that inhibits and restricts teachers as it greatly affects both the subject they teach and the methods they employ to teach it.

Similar researches have been carried out in Greece. Chatzisavvidis (2007) studies the curriculum for the Greek language course for lower secondary school and the corresponding student and teacher textbooks. He argues that progress has been made in the context of multiliteracies compared to previous materials, citing references to multimodality, the social dimension of language and the need to cultivate critically literate students. Despite these advancements, he maintains that effective implementation of the 'multiliteracies approach' heavily relies on teachers' adept utilization of existing materials. However, he observes that this compatibility is primarily theoretical, as textbook texts often do not align with the four-stage approach proposed by the theory of multiliteracies. Recognizing the significant influence of language textbooks on teaching methods, Chatzisavvidis (2007) ultimately concludes that practical implementation of the multiliteracies trend appears to be hindered in practice.

Several years later, Dimasi and Aravani (2013) conducted research with the same subject and they obtained similar results. They observed that the curriculum shows both direct and indirect conceptual connections with the pedagogy of multiliteracies. Additionally, they identified multiliteracy exercises in student textbooks, primarily focusing on the creation of texts using a multimodal approach. They emphasized the pivotal role of teachers in the proper instructional use of these activities highlighting the need for substantial additional training for teachers.

Finally, it is worth making a brief reference to research carried out at the level of higher education which also supports the pedagogical and cognitive advantages that can result from the use of multiliteracies (Castro Garcés, 2021; Nabhan & Hidayat, 2018; Yeh, 2018). At the same time, they point out the necessity of turning curriculums and textbooks towards the pedagogy of multiliteracies, arguing that it is the most appropriate framework for language teaching (Allen & Paesani, 2010; Corkett & Benevides, 2015). In addition to the previously mentioned points, they also emphasize another aspect of the issue. They connect the utilization of multiliteracies in the educational process with the appropriate preparation of future teachers. They argue that this is a practical approach to familiarize teachers with innovative teaching methods and provide them with the necessary knowledge to enable the integration of multiliteracies in their future classrooms (Allen & Paesani, 2010; Corkett & Benevides, 2015).

3. Method

The purpose of this research was to investigate the Greek language teachers' opinions regarding the role and position of multiliteracies in language teaching contexts in secondary education. This specific perspective was chosen due to a gap in the existing literature. Additionally, it takes into consideration the numerous studies emphasizing the pivotal role of teachers in these teaching practices and the need to focus on research in this direction. In particular, there are four research questions: (1) How do Greek language teachers define the concept of multiliteracies? (2) What is the place of multiliteracies in language teaching? (3) How do students respond to the use of multiliteracies? (4) Do Greek Language teachers feel adequate in the use of multiliteracies?

3.1. Participants

The research sample included 10 language teachers who were teaching the 'Greek language' course in public secondary schools. Their participation was voluntary, and they were selected through 'snowball' sampling method. Eight of the participants were women, and two were men—aged between 45 and 55. Their teaching experiences range from 10 to 30 years. Finally, regarding their

qualifications, two of them hold a bachelor's degree, two others mentioned that they hold two bachelor's degrees, four hold a master's degree, and two hold a Doctorate degree.

3.2. Procedure

The semi-structured interview was selected as the most suitable research tool for data collection. It comprised the following sections: (a) delineation of multiliteracies, (b) multiliteracies and language teaching, (c) students' response, (d) adequacy of teachers in the use of multiliteracies. The interviews were conducted individually and were tape-recorded. The research material resulting from their transcription was analyzed qualitatively through the following procedures which were suggested by Miles and Huberman (1994):

- (1) Data Reduction: The first component of data analysis involved first and second level coding and pattern coding, which involves placing descriptive or conceptual tags. Codes resulted in groups of categories, which were "labelled" by a specific name tag. Afterwards, similar concepts with common characteristics were clustered into themes, to reduce the number of categories.
- (2) Data Display: On the second level of analysis, data were tabulated and displayed in individual tables and in crosschecking formats.
- (3) Conclusion Drawing: Finally, the third level of data analysis involved conclusion drawing. A text presenting the obtained data was drafted, including quotations from the interviewees. The latter was essential because it shaped the phases of data collection and contributed to the emergence of the ultimate findings of the study (cf. Griva & Stamou, 2014).

4. Results

From the analysis, 120 codes were resulted, which were grouped into 13 categories, and these were clustered into four themes (thematic strands): (1) conceptual approach to multiliteracies, (2) multiliteracies and teaching, (3) student's response, and (4) training and educational needs of language teachers.

4.1. Conceptual approach to multiliteracies

Most of the participants in the study defined multiliteracies as a new approach to language that "*moved away from traditional standards*" (Participant 1) and brought a "*refreshing perspective to teaching*" (Participant 5). Many of them viewed multiliteracies as a "*tool*" (Participant 2) for describing and addressing modern communication methods and the ways used for this purpose. They

emphasized the necessity of shifting language teaching in this direction and utilizing appropriate materials. For this reason, some of them identified multiliteracies with teaching that was achieved “*by combining linguistic texts and other elements*” (Participant 8) or even “*using multimodal texts with the aim of making the language more easily understandable in all its dimensions*” (Participant 10). For some others, the interest was focused on the teaching design part and on the “*various techniques*” which could be utilized by teachers in this context—that is, “*every medium and every way in which a message could be delivered to the students*” (Participant 3). At the same time, a small part of the participants mentioned the role of technology and its direct connection to language and education as well as the possibility of “*using a variety of text formats that were also related to new technologies*” (Participant 7).

When describing the characteristics of multiliteracies, most participants emphasized the potential they provided for integrating various media in language teaching, particularly highlighting multimodal and multimedia texts as primary examples. For many of the participants, multiliteracies referred to an “*innovative*” (Participant 4) and “*very promising*” (Participant 6) teaching approach, since they “*manage to modernize teaching*” (Participant 1) and effectively incorporate technology in it, giving, in this way, a creative character to all educational processes. Many participants associated this teaching dimension with the “*teaching freedoms*” (Participant 9) granted to teachers and the resulting benefits for students. They observed one of the key features of multiliteracies as the diversity and flexibility they provided in selecting teaching methods. Others emphasized the impact multiliteracies had on different “*types of students,*” considering factors, such as their background, grades, etc. According to this group, multiliteracies “*make teaching an accessible process for all*” (Participant 3). They infuse it with an interactive element, enabling even non-participating students to engage and effectively get involved in the educational process. Furthermore, the capacity to offer differentiated instruction reinforces this fact, as “*each teacher can employ multiliteracies to customize teaching according to the level and needs of their students*” (Participant 9). Finally, for some participants, a feature of multiliteracies was the activation of students’ senses and thinking, as well as their contribution to the development and cultivation of many skills and abilities. As they typically mentioned: “*many times a simple text might not say anything to the students. On the other hand, when we used a multimodal text, we activated all of the students’ senses*” (Participant 3). For instance, “*an illustration made them perceive colors, motion, and numbers in a statistics table. At that moment, a child’s mind operated in a different way. It did not insist just on the words in front of it but began to get concerned about them and think in a different and more critical way*” (Participant 8).

Regarding the opinion that participants had about multiliteracies, most of them considered it to be an integral part of everyday life, since *“multimodal texts were dominant in modern multicultural and technologically developed societies”* (Participant 7). For many of them, they were directly connected to the language course and were characterized as *“a subject that should be taught in language classes”* (Participant 2) seeing that *“schools are obliged to prepare students for the new communicative environment”* (Participant 5). As they characteristically stated, *“since we live in the era of the image, we should give students the opportunity to familiarize themselves with these forms of speech, these ways of conveying messages”* (Participant 2). Furthermore, *“it’s an opportunity to see any subject from a different perspective, such as a sketch, a film or a song or even imagine various things”* (Participant 10).

Some others considered multiliteracies to be a new and particularly interesting teaching subject, whilst others treated them as a *“useful tool that gives another dimension of teaching”* (Participant 6). For many the impact of their use on students was equally important. Most of them focused on provoking students’ interest and their active participation in the educational process, while others considered them to be a necessary element for the development and strengthening of students’ judgment and cognitive skills, as in the lessons in which they were used *“students came into contact and mastered knowledge in many different ways”* (Participant 4), *“practiced the multiplicity and complexity of meanings,”* (Participant 6) *“were involved in a meaningful way in processes of comparison, confrontation and approaching an object from different perspectives”* (Participant 4). In this context, some argued that students *“came into contact with the language itself and the various linguistic phenomena”* (Participant 6) and acquired metacognitive and metalinguistic skills. Finally, some participants argued that multiliteracies are the most suitable approach for teaching multicultural classes because of the fact that *“they offer the opportunity for all students, even those who do not know the language, to participate in the teaching process. For example, an image and its intended message can be understood by someone who does not speak Greek”* (Participant 3).

4.2. Multiliteracies and teaching

Regarding the presence of multiliteracies in the curriculum, most participants stated that it is suggestive, since *“there is no explicit reference to them nor is there a clear framework for their utilization”* (Participant 1), but they are presented only *“indirectly and suggestively through the objectives and activities suggested”* (Participant 8). For many participants, their presence is evident but to a very limited extent. As they argued, *“there are some relevant references in curricula, but these only suggest a direction. From there on, each teacher chooses the path to be taken”* (Participant 9). Therefore, for several of them, the limited

presence of multiliteracies means their optional use. Some others openly expressed their dissatisfaction with their unsatisfactory presence pointing out that *“the curricula are anachronistic and outdated”* (Participant 5) and in fact, *“this works to the detriment of students since school does not prepare them according to today’s standards”* (Participant 5). For this reason, some emphasized that the curricula *“should have been modernized and take into account the new data and needs of the modern era”* (Participant 7) giving *“special importance to the new ways and means of communication”* (Participant 6). Some acknowledged that in recent years, steps have been taken towards this direction and in the recent curriculum *“multiliteracies were more explicitly and strongly emphasized”* (Participant 4).

When they were asked about the presence of multiliteracies in language school textbooks, most participants stated that it is satisfactory since *“as much as possible, several texts are multimodal”* (Participant 2). Some argued that the most indicative example of their presence are digital books, *“which are enriched with hyperlinks and refer, in every case, to material of various formats and topics”* (Participant 10). What is more, several participants referred to 12th Grade new books and found that *“a relevant effort is being made,” “an opening towards this direction”* (Participant 4). Indeed, there were those who considered that the presence of multiliteracies is limited *“in relation to the dissemination and influence they have in everyday life”* (Participant 5) and emphasized the urgent need for modernization of school textbooks in order to *“keep up with the circumstances and needs of the era”* (Participant 5).

Regarding the role of multiliteracies in the teaching of the Greek language, most participants mentioned that they make an effort to use them regularly and seize every opportunity, across all stages of teaching. They recognized *“their contribution to the improvement of teaching”* (Participant 1) and *“the positive impact they have on students”* (Participant 3). Some of them specified that they employ multiliteracies at the initiation phase during the introduction and presentation of new knowledge. They do this in the belief that it captures their students’ attention and makes *“the transition to new knowledge smoother”* (Participant 7). In fact, several participants referred to the use of videos stressing that *“it is much more useful for children to see the practical application than to read a definition”* (Participant 10), *“as for example in the case of style and its change according to the communication condition. Reading a rule about formal speech and seeing an actual formal speech are two different experiences. Through video, you can observe not only linguistic choices but also expressions and body language, aspects that cannot be fully comprehended through other means”* (Participant 8). Furthermore, some educators employed multiliteracies to facilitate their students’ practice aiding in the comprehension and application of new knowledge. In this case, the participants stated that they sought to involve the students in *“various every day and natural communication*

situations" (Participant 9), *"in processes that would cultivate the oral language, mainly through dialogue and dramatization, but also the written language through the creation of different kinds of texts"* (Participant 2) in order to *"put into practice what was taught"* (Participant 9). In this context, some other participants also included the students' presentations and the creation of multimodal texts since, as they stated, *"students should have had an active role in the educational process"* (Participant 10), *"they should, at every opportunity, take initiatives, create and present their work"* (Participant 9). Finally, certain participants mentioned that they utilized multiliteracies so that they can provide feedback to their students, particularly during the reflection phase. They aimed to *"assess the outcomes of teaching, the students' achievements and areas that require review"* (Participant 1).

Regarding the reasons why participants seek to utilize multiliteracies in their teaching and the goals they set, almost everyone agreed that the primary reason is to change the character of teaching. They argued that *"by incorporating multiliteracies, teaching becomes more interesting and accessible"* (Participant 1), thereby achieving the goal of activation and greater participation of students. At the same time, many argued that there are also cognitive benefits since multiliteracies enable them to approach knowledge in many different ways and achieve a better understanding of the course by the students and also appeal to many different types of students. In the same way, they manage to offer knowledge to all of their students and include them in the educational process *"even the weakest students, students who would hesitate to speak in another traditional context"* (Participant 4), *"even students who have difficulty expressing themselves or students who do not speak Greek fluently"* (Participant 3). Besides, for many participants, an important reason for using multiliteracies was the cultivation of students' creative expression. They believe that multiliteracies provide students with the chance *"to express themselves freely"* (Participant 8) allowing them to *"use language and convey their message in a way that aligns with their feelings and self-expression"* (Participant 7). Doing so, they argued, directly engages students in linguistic processes of speech production, thereby *"moving teaching and learning away from rigid and established standards and turning them into an enjoyable process for students"* (Participant 8). In addition to that, several of the participants stated that their goal is to bring students into contact with various genres and types of texts as *"they are an essential part of the language course"* and *"knowing their conventions is one of the basic conditions for effective communication"* (Participant 2). Simultaneously, many of them aimed for students to engage with diverse messages and the various means through which these messages were conveyed in each text. Hence, they found it beneficial for children to encounter *"an alternative perspective, possibly the opposing viewpoint, in connection with the text being taught in the book, presented through methods*

such as a sketch, a song or any other medium" (Participant 4). In this way, students will eventually learn, among other things, to critically approach the texts they read and the information they convey, to compare the opinions those texts present, and at the same time they will develop other skills, such as composing, analyzing and evaluating the information they receive. For some others, the use of multiliteracies in teaching aimed at the gradual construction and acquisition of knowledge, since they *"actively involve students in various linguistic processes and help them in an experiential way to gradually master all structures of language"* (Participant 9). At the same time, multiliteracies also help to cultivate students' initiative, mainly through the opportunity they provide for effective presentations of their work. This serves as *"a strong initiative for the students"* and *"they feel immense satisfaction when they have the opportunity to express themselves"* (Participant 10). Yet, a teacher's perspective was different (i.e., Participant 7). He believed that the use of multiliteracies in teaching becomes obligatory due to their inclusion in school textbooks.

4.3. Student's response

In this section, the data which dealt with students' response to the use of multiliteracies in language teaching are presented. Most participants stated that they noticed students' enthusiasm, as *"children felt more at ease in this teaching context because they had transitioned away from written text, which they perceive as outdated"* (Participant 6). On the whole, *"images, digital speech and sound dominate their daily lives and when these are utilized in teaching, it is expected that their interest will increase"* (Participant 2). Many participants linked multiliteracies to enjoyable learning and increased student engagement in the educational process. They claimed that *"the children show in every way that they want this change"* (Participant 1), *"they exhibit fearlessness, engage effortlessly and participate without stress"* (Participant 3) and *"many times they take initiatives, they bring relevant material that impressed them so that we can all understand it together"* (Participant 4). Hence, there are also some participants who noted that children express a desire for more frequent use of multiliteracies and even wish to create their own multimodal materials. This led some to the conclusion that, due to multiliteracies, students' self-confidence increases since *"children want to have an active role in teaching, they want to experiment and express themselves in various ways without the fear of making a mistake or unacceptable [sic]"* (Participant 7). Indeed, there were some participants who observed that the response of each student is different and often this is also related to the medium used in each case. Therefore, most of the time, they leave the choice to their students. Besides, *"multiliteracies give everyone the opportunity to express themselves in their own way. One can engage in an activity, another one can create a collage, a third one can describe it, and*

yet another one can provide an analysis" (Participant 8). Finally, there were also a few participants who noted that there is also a small portion of students who face multiliteracies with hesitation and difficulty as they are not particularly familiar with them.

Regarding the learning benefits resulting from the use of multiliteracies in language teaching, almost all participants reported a better understanding of the subject. They argued that multiliteracies enable them *"to approach language and each individual subject in many different ways"* (Participant 1) making *"knowledge accessible to all students"* (Participant 3). As a participant stated, *"children observe that through a presentation that contains figures, images, examples, videos, etc., they understand the meaning of the lesson much better and ask for more similar teaching practices"* (Participant 8). Furthermore, in the view of some, enhanced comprehension is directly associated with students' language proficiency, improved expressive skills and overall communication skill development. This occurs as students *"encounter authentic language"* (Participant 1), *"learn the language through experience"* (Participant 10), and *"learn by doing"* (Participant 1). They supported that *"children do not simply memorize basic rules. They acquire the ability to use language accurately, adapting it to meet their own needs, instead"* (Participant 9). An equally important learning benefit for many participants was the students' exposure to and familiarity with different types of texts, their conventions and the functions they perform. Exactly the same applies to students' exposure to new technologies. As several of the participants reported, through the use of multiliteracies in teaching, students *"gain familiarity with technology and its role in language and communication"* (Participant 7). Children *"learn the language itself and how it adapts to the medium employed and the message it aims to convey"* (Participant 7). This contact and familiarization gives them the opportunity to be able to create material themselves, *"to use multiliteracies in practice"* (Participant 3), *"to create multimodal material"* (Participant 2), *"to present their work in many different ways"* (Participant 3), i.e. *"to master digital literacy"* (Participant 2). Besides, several of the participants argued that multiliteracies contribute to the development of students' mental processes and some referred to individual skills that are developed, such as critical thinking, critical ability, creativity, cooperation, initiative, and the development of metacognitive skills. For them students' engagement with multiliteracies *"acts as a driving force for student thinking"* (Participant 4). They found that *"students wonder"* (Participant 3), *"engage in processes of comparing texts and opinions"* (Participant 4) and *"compare different ways of conveying a message"* (Participant 7). At the same time, they *"take initiatives"* (Participant 3), *"produce material"* (Participant 4), *"learn to work in groups"* (Participant 6), *"cooperate with their classmates to achieve a common goal"* (Participant 7) and *"after a certain point, they regulate*

the way they learn, the way they work, the way they generally deal with the world" (Participant 1). Namely, they acquire skills that will be of utmost importance for their future studies and their life in general.

Regarding the assessment, all the participants who participated in the research stated that they follow the standard of teaching. Therefore, they use different assessment methods each time, "*depending on the subject of the evaluation*" (Participant 6) and "*the student profile*" (Participant 3). Most participants clarified that they do not evaluate only the result or the final product but also they mainly focus on the overall presence of the students and the process of creating the deliverables. They are more interested in "*the attitude*" (Participant 10) and "*the students' willingness*" (Participant 3), "*their participation in all procedures*" (Participant 10) and "*the way they cooperated with their classmates*" (Participant 3), stressing that "*these are also essential elements that should be rewarded regardless of the final result*" (Participant 10). On the other hand, there are those who focused on the cognitive part and declared that through the evaluation they are interested in ascertaining whether the goals they had set have been achieved and whether their students have finally consolidated new knowledge. For them, "*the result of each task and the way in which students will present it*" (Participant 2) is of great importance. They seek to determine "*whether there has been any advancement*" (Participant 2), "*if the children have truly grasped what they have been taught and if they can effectively apply it*" (Participant 4). Equally important to some is the assessment of students' judgment. They considered that "*children should learn to deal critically with everything happening around them*" (Participant 1). Therefore, they evaluate "*the way they deal with knowledge but also what is asked of them*" (Participant 8) since they do not want their students to be "*passive receivers, but critical thinking people in every level*" (Participant 1). For some others, the most important is the students' way of expressing themselves and for their assessment, it is taken into account "*whether they can express what they want using the language and the means at their disposal correctly,*" that is, whether the students can "*make the appropriate choices, to choose the appropriate way and means of expression for a particular occasion*" (Participant 7). Finally, there were also a few participants who differed. They stated that multiliteracies are "*a new,*" "*fluid*" and "*constantly evolving*" subject for them (Participant 5). In consequence, they are therefore unable to assess their students in their use.

4.4. Training and educational needs of language teachers

Most of the participants who took part in the research stated that they did not feel adequate in the use of multiliteracies in their teaching. As for the main reason, they cited their incomplete training on the specific subject as most of them belong to the "*older generation,*" which was rooted in "*the era of books*"

and written language" (Participant 2) and during their studies they were not taught anything relevant. As they pointed out, *"everything is evolving: society, technology, education, teaching methods"* (Participant 5) and *"in order to follow this development, experience and observation alone are not enough. Correct and targeted information is needed"* (Participant 7). Hence, most of them admitted that their relevant training is necessary *"so as to keep the teaching process in line with our era"* (Participant 5). Only a few distinguished themselves and asserted their competence and confidence in using multiliteracies. For them, multiliteracies are included either in the category of *"general knowledge"* that they have acquired through personal search or they were a subject of teaching in some educational program they attended.

Regardless of whether the participants feel adequate or not in the use of multiliteracies, they all recommend the institutionalization of systematic further training. They described further training as necessary and indispensable not only for the issue of multiliteracies but for anything new that arises in the field of education as they consider it the only way to allow them to adequately respond to the challenges. For this reason, many argued that further training should be mandatory in order to *"ensure that all teachers are properly informed"* (Participant 5). As for the content of the training, some suggested the existence of training programs that will have laboratory nature *"in small groups, teachers will apply in practice what was presented to them on a theoretical level"* (Participant 1). In addition, some considered it crucial to provide appropriate training material which they can refer to after the end of the training, while some argued that there should be an online help platform where the trainers would respond immediately to any difficulties the trainees encounter during lessons.

Regarding the entities that could potentially administer such training, the majority of participants suggested that it should be managed on a central level, under the jurisdiction of an official state agency. Many believed that the Ministry of Education is more appropriate *"as the competent ministry of all matters related to education"* (Participant 2) but also *"as an institution that has the capacity to support mass training"* (Participant 4). Several also mentioned the Institute of Educational Policy as they argue that *"it possesses both the means and the know-how"* (Participant 7). Some others considered that training should have a more *"familiar character"* and for this reason, they suggested that it be carried out at the local level either by the Coordinator of Educational Project of Scientific Responsibility or by the Coordinator of Educational Project of Pedagogical Responsibility. For them they are two *"reference people"* (Participant 1), *"the main two sources of help"* (Participant 6) who know the strengths and weaknesses of the teachers they support. Therefore, if they are responsible for training, they will be able to adjust it according to the needs of the specific teachers and ensure better results. On the other hand, there are

participants who mentioned university departments arguing that *“these are closer to research and innovation”* and *“have a better insight into what is happening in the educational systems of other countries”* (Participant 5). Finally, a few participants differentiated themselves and declared that education *“is a purely personal matter”* (Participant 10), *“a matter of personal responsibility”* (Participant 9) and *“personal choice.”* Therefore, *“each teacher should freely choose when, by whom and in what way he/she will be trained”* (Participant 10).

5. Conclusion

The results of this research demonstrate that participants have a solid grasp of the concept of multiliteracies both in theory and in practice. They described their characteristics, their position and role in society and in education, and they identified relevant references in the official educational material for language courses, such as the curriculum and school textbooks. In addition, they mentioned the various ways in which they choose to use multiliteracies in language teaching and the reasons that lead to use them, pointing out students' positive reaction and the resulting learning benefits. Nevertheless, the participants stated that they do not feel particularly confident in using multiliteracies. For this reason, they emphasized the need for their further training and made specific proposals regarding its form and content, as well as the institutions they would like to see implement it.

Based on the above results, the present research confirms the findings of previous research (see, for example, Allen, 2008; Askildson, 2008; Boche, 2014; Chatzisavvidis, 2007; Dimasi & Aravani, 2013; Kiss & Mizusawa, 2018; Lim et al., 2020; Rajendram, 2015) and at the same time, it highlights the importance of investigating issues related to practical application ‘in the classroom’ from a teacher’s perspective. Assuming that shedding light on teachers’ perspectives and actions, along with their concerns, they can significantly contribute to the academic discourse, we urge that researchers consider exploring these issues from a teacher’s standpoint.

Authors’ Statement

The authors discussed and drafted the article together. All authors collaborated in writing all sections of this paper.

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